

**Article Title: Security and privacy in physical activity chatbots on social media:
A scoping review**

List of rejected articles after full-text screening (n=25)

NO SOCIAL MEDIA (N=23)
Albers N, Hizli B, Scheltinga BL, Meijer E, Brinkman WP. Setting Physical Activity Goals with a Virtual Coach: Vicarious Experiences, Personalization and Acceptance. <i>J Med Syst.</i> 2023;47(1):15. doi:10.1007/s10916-022-01899-9
Bickmore TW, Schulman D, Sidner C. Automated interventions for multiple health behaviors using conversational agents. <i>Patient Educ Couns.</i> 2013;92(2):142-8. doi:10.1016/j.pec.2013.05.011
Bickmore TW, Silliman RA, Nelson K, et al. A randomized controlled trial of an automated exercise coach for older adults. <i>J Am Geriatr Soc.</i> 2013;61(10):1676-83. doi:10.1111/jgs.12449
Chauvin R, Clavel C, Sabouret N, Ravenet B. A virtual coach with more or less empathy: impact on older adults' engagement to exercise. Proceedings of the 23rd ACM International Conference on Intelligent Virtual Agents; Würzburg, Germany: Association for Computing Machinery; 2023. p. 1-9. doi:10.1145/3570945.3607338
Eguchi A, Kawamura Y, Kawashima T, et al. The Efficacy of an mHealth App in Facilitating Weight Loss Among Japanese Fitness Center Members: Regression Analysis Study. <i>JMIR Form Res.</i> 2023;7:e48435. doi:10.2196/48435
Figuroa CA, Luo TC, Jacobo A, et al. Conversational Physical Activity Coaches for Spanish and English Speaking Women: A User Design Study. <i>Front Digit Health.</i> 2021;3:747153. doi:10.3389/fdgth.2021.747153
Gardiner PM, McCue KD, Negash LM, et al. Engaging women with an embodied conversational agent to deliver mindfulness and lifestyle recommendations: A feasibility randomized control trial. <i>Patient Education and Counseling.</i> 2017;100(9):1720-9. doi: https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2017.04.015
Hahn L, Rathbun SL, Schmidt MD, Johnsen K, Annesi JJ, Ahn SJG. Using Virtual Agents and Activity Monitors to Autonomously Track and Assess Self-Determined Physical Activity Among Young Children: A 6-Week Feasibility Field Study. <i>Cyberpsychol Behav Soc Netw.</i> 2020;23(7):471-8. doi:10.1089/cyber.2019.0491
IJsselsteijn WA, Kort YAWd, Westerink J, Jager Md, Bonants R. Virtual Fitness: Stimulating Exercise Behavior through Media Technology. <i>Presence.</i> 2006;15(6):688-98. doi:10.1162/pres.15.6.688
King AC, Campero I, Sheats JL, et al. Testing the comparative effects of physical activity advice by humans vs. computers in underserved populations: The COMPASS trial design, methods, and baseline characteristics. <i>Contemp Clin Trials.</i> 2017;61:115-25. doi:10.1016/j.cct.2017.07.020
Kowatsch T, Lohse KM, Erb V, et al. Hybrid Ubiquitous Coaching with a Novel Combination of Mobile and Holographic Conversational Agents Targeting Adherence to Home Exercises: Four Design and Evaluation Studies. <i>J Med Internet Res.</i> 2021;23(2):e23612. doi:10.2196/23612
Kramer JN, Künzler F, Mishra V, et al. Which Components of a Smartphone Walking App Help Users to Reach Personalized Step Goals? Results From an Optimization Trial. <i>Ann Behav Med.</i> 2020;54(7):518-28. doi:10.1093/abm/kaaa002

Krishnakumar A, Verma R, Chawla R, et al. Evaluating Glycemic Control in Patients of South Asian Origin with Type 2 Diabetes Using a Digital Therapeutic Platform: Analysis of Real-World Data. <i>J Med Internet Res.</i> 2021;23(3):e17908. doi:10.2196/17908
Künzler F, Mishra V, Kramer JN, Kotz D, Fleisch E, Kowatsch T. Exploring the State-of-Receptivity for mHealth Interventions. <i>Proc ACM Interact Mob Wearable Ubiquitous Technol.</i> 2019;3(4). doi:10.1145/3369805
Louvet A, Ravenet B, Clavel C, Sabouret N. Interaction avec un agent motivationnel pour soutenir le changement de comportement: Interaction with a Motivational Agent to Support Behaviour Change. <i>Adjunct Proceedings of the 32nd Conference on l'Interaction Homme-Machine; Virtual Event, France: Association for Computing Machinery; 2022.</i> p. Article 12. doi:10.1145/3451148.3458647
Moore R, Al-Tamimi AK, Freeman E. Investigating the Potential of a Conversational Agent (Phyllis) to Support Adolescent Health and Overcome Barriers to Physical Activity: Co-Design Study. <i>JMIR Form Res.</i> 2024;8:e51571. doi:10.2196/51571
Ollier J, Suryapalli P, Fleisch E, et al. Can digital health researchers make a difference during the pandemic? Results of the single-arm, chatbot-led Elena+: Care for COVID-19 interventional study. <i>Front Public Health.</i> 2023;11:1185702. doi:10.3389/fpubh.2023.1185702
Pirolli P, Youngblood GM, Du H, Konrad A, Nelson L, Springer A. Scaffolding the mastery of healthy behaviors with Fittle+ systems: Evidence-based interventions and theory. <i>Human-Computer Interaction.</i> 2021;36(2):73-106. doi: https://dx.doi.org/10.1080/07370024.2018.1512414
Sakane N, Suganuma A, Domichi M, et al. The Effect of a mHealth App (KENPO-app) for Specific Health Guidance on Weight Changes in Adults with Obesity and Hypertension: Pilot Randomized Controlled Trial. <i>JMIR Mhealth Uhealth.</i> 2023;11:e43236. doi:10.2196/43236
Stasinaki A, Büchter D, Shih CI, et al. Effects of a novel mobile health intervention compared to a multi-component behaviour changing program on body mass index, physical capacities and stress parameters in adolescents with obesity: a randomized controlled trial. <i>BMC Pediatr.</i> 2021;21(1):308. doi:10.1186/s12887-021-02781-2
Wu IY, Yu Y, Cheng S-J, Tu W-J, Sung T-J. Acceptance and sustainability of health promotion solutions for the elderly in Taiwan: evidence from SHI-LIN elderly university in Taipei. <i>Proceedings of the 12th ACM International Conference on PErvasive Technologies Related to Assistive Environments; Rhodes, Greece: Association for Computing Machinery; 2019.</i> p. 21–7. doi:10.1145/3316782.3321529
Zhou S, Zhang Z, Bickmore T, editors. Adapting a Persuasive Conversational Agent for the Chinese Culture. <i>2017 International Conference on Culture and Computing (Culture and Computing); 2017 10-12 Sept. 2017.</i> doi:10.1109/Culture.and.Computing.2017.42
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Stein N, Brooks K. A Fully Automated Conversational Artificial Intelligence for Weight Loss: Longitudinal Observational Study Among Overweight and Obese Adults. <i>JMIR diabetes.</i> 2017;2(2):e28. doi:10.2196/diabetes.8590
CHATBOT FOR NON-PHYSICAL ACTIVITY PART OF INTERVENTION (N=2)
Sy B, Wassil M, Connelly H, Hassan A. Behavioral Predictive Analytics Towards Personalization for Self-management: a Use Case on Linking Health-Related Social Needs. <i>SN Comput Sci.</i> 2022;3(3):237. doi:10.1007/s42979-022-01092-2
Vu B, Bruchhaus S, Moorhead A, et al., editors. Towards Continuous Professional Monitoring of Health Status Based on Energetic Balancing. <i>2022 IEEE International Workshop on Sport, Technology and Research (STAR); 2022 6-8 July 2022.</i> doi:10.1109/STAR53492.2022.9859599